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THE ENERGY-ABSORBING CHARACTERISTICS OF COMPOSITE TUBE-REINFORCED ALUMINUM FOAMS UNDER COMPRESSION

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Introduction

- Energy-absorbing materials have been a significant topic in the field of buffering protection in recent years. Extensive testing on various types of structure and material shows that composite materials can provide outstanding energy-absorbing characteristics. This paper investigates the energy-absorbing characteristics of the aluminum foams containing embedded carbon fiber reinforced epoxy (CFRE) tubes by quasi-static compression tests in order to find a ideal combination of them. Hopefully, the result would help development of composite material in buffering protection industry.

Experimental Procedure

Table 1. Specimens of CFRE tubes

Sample ID	Internal diameter, D (mm)	Thickness, t (mm)	D/t	Mass (g)	Energy absorbed (J)	SEA (kJ/kg)
T1	10	2.5	4.0	4.45	324.87	73.00
T2	11	2.0	5.5	3.78	245.75	65.01
T3	12	1.5	8.0	2.86	182.48	63.80
T4	13	1.0	13.0	2.03	161.73	79.67
T5	14	0.5	28.0	1.11	63.04	56.79

Table 2. Specimens of aluminum foams filled with CFRP tubes

Sample ID	CFRE tube ID	Number of tubes	Mass(g)	Energy absorbed (J)	SEA (kJ/kg)
P1	---	0	234.51	1265.43	5.40
P2	T1	3	220.63	1665.92	7.55
P3	T1	5	242.43	2262.67	9.33
P4	T1	7	251.11	2693.89	10.73
P5	T2	7	224.29	2219.10	9.89
P6	T3	7	201.34	1810.60	8.99
P7	T4	7	237.39	1776.96	7.48
P8	T5	7	224.42	1116.33	4.97
P9	---		221.47	697.73	3.15

The quasi-static compression tests were undertaken at a crosshead displacement rate of 1 mm/min and interrupted when the crosshead had travelled at least 20 mm. Load and displacement of crosshead were recorded by the sensor of testing machine. The specific energy absorption (SEA) of the samples was determined from the energy under the load-displacement trace and the initial mass of the specimen.

Result and Discussion

- Figure 1 shows typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on tubes with different values of the ratio of internal diameter to thickness (D/t). All five traces exhibited similar characteristics, with failure occurring in a stable manner at an approximately constant force after an initial peak. Table 1 indicates that the energy absorbed during compression increased with the values of D/t . Specimen T4 had the highest SEA and T1 came in second, while T1 absorbed twice as much energy as T4 did. Consider the total energy and SEA factors comprehensively, T1 would possess the most efficient energy-absorbing ability.

Figure 1. Typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on tubes with different values of D/t

- Figure 2 and Figure 3 shows the typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on aluminum foams filled with tubes. According to Figure 2, in the case of the same thickness of CFRE tubes, with the increase of the number of CFRE tubes, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the specimen increased, and the length of the platform decreased. When the numbers of CFRE tubes were same, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the specimen increased with the increase of the thickness of CFRE tubes, and the length of the platform decreased, as shown in Figure 3. Table 2 indicates that specimen P4 had the highest SEA, which possessed the maximum number and thickness of the CFRE tubes. The SEA of CFRP tube was much higher than that of aluminum foam, so the SEA can be effectively improved by inserting CFRP tubes into aluminum foam material.

Figure 2 and 3. Typical load–displacement traces following compression tests on aluminum foams filled with tubes

Conclusions

- A novel tube-reinforced plane structure has been developed in which CFRE tubes are embedded in aluminum foams with low density. Initial tests on CFRE tubes shows that the energy absorbed during compression increases with the values of D/t while the SEA maximizes at D/t equals 13 when the external diameter is constant. Then a series compression tests on the aluminum foams containing embedded CFRE tubes indicates that in the case of the same thickness of CFRE tubes, with the increase of the number of CFRE tubes, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the composite material increase, and the length of the platform decreases. When the numbers of CFRE tubes are same, the platform stress and overall stiffness of the composite material increase with the increase of the thickness of CFRP tubes, and the length of the platform decreases.
- The SEA of CFRE tubes is much higher than that of aluminum foam, so the SEA can be effectively improved by inserting CFRE tubes into aluminum foam material. However, at the same time, they also increase the stress level during deformation. In the concrete design of protection structure, considering the protecting and economic requirements comprehensively, the aluminum foam material with lower stress level should be used as far as possible while the use of CFRE tubes should be controlled in a reasonable range.

THANK YOU !

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